

Expeditious method for mapping soil's organic matter

Introduction

Soil organic matter is a key variable in soil analyses, used by farmers in pasture management and in the assessment of soil carbon sequestration. This assessment requires a rapid survey of soil samples in large quantities, capable of cost-effectively, covering large areas and assessing spatial heterogeneity for the application of differentiated management recommendations.

The aim of the project was to develop an expeditious and low-cost method for mapping soil organic matter and for analyzing carbon sequestration in biodiverse sown pastures in agricultural and agro-forestry areas. The method used visible and near-infrared (VNIR) spectroscopy, using field sensors and satellite images.

Experimental data collection was carried out on 7 agricultural properties, between 2018 and 2021. Soil samples were collected in 25 ha plots and the choice of sampling points was based on measurements of soil electrical conductivity.

Sampling was carried out using mechanical and automatic collection equipment. The measurement of organic matter was carried out conventionally, in the laboratory, and also using near-infrared spectroscopy, using a spectrometer.

The results obtained were correlated with satellite data and pasture management practices, measured during field visits.

Lessons learned

Soil organic matter (SOM) is an indicator of the evolution of soil fertility in the Montado Mediterranean ecosystem. There is a significant correlation between NIRS calibration models and reference methods to quantify these soil parameters (R^2 , 0.85 and RPD, 2.7), which can mean an important simplification of the time and costs involved, better suited to the needs of the current agricultural production management. To go further, in a perspective of PA, two research topics require further attention:

- (i) improvement of portable spectrometers in order to achieve a more accurate response in direct field measurements and
- (ii) further exploration of soil spectral information obtained through satellites (remote sensing).

Future research along any of these lines will involve more advanced technologies, such as the use of methods drawn from the field of artificial intelligence.

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Figure 1. Map with the locations of the soil sampling.

Figure 2. Soil sampling methodology.

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Further information

<https://www.terraprima.pt/pt/projecto/24>

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